

‘Material effects’: The role of materials in people’s product evaluations

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Abstract

Materials, offering distinctive characteristics, are key factors in design to improve products. They do not only improve ‘use and function’, but also the creation of products’ meanings. Materials can have remarkable influence on people’s appraisals of products. Stemming from this context, this paper is concerned with addressing the role of materials in people’s products evaluations. Moreover, how these evaluations differentiate based on particular product categories.

This paper consists of a field study conducted with 16 participants who were asked to evaluate products and materials in 6 categories of products; (1) a small electronic product, (2) a product made of a material they like, (3) a product made of a material they dislike, (4) a product with a distinct function like sitting/ storing/ eating or writing on it/ lighting, (5) a big electronic product and (6) a favourite product. The answers of the participants were screened for the descriptions collected under seven basic parameters: use, function, materials, sensorial properties, perceptions, associations and emotions. The materials descriptions of the selected products were also examined and grouped under similar parameters, which were defined as the components of *material experiences* for this study. The results were analyzed and used for the creation of two models; the Product Experiences Evaluation Model (PEEM) and the Material Experiences Evaluation Model (MEEM) expressing the parameters of people’s materials and products interactions. The models showed that while evaluating the materials of products, people do not merely concentrate on the physical characteristics of materials but also some non-physical ones, such as sensorial characteristics or perceptive characteristics of materials.

Keywords: materials and design, material experiences, product experiences

1 Introduction

Materials are one of the key factors in design for creating product values. They do not only provide a technical superiority for products, but also support the meanings of products. Hodgson and Harper (2004) state that materials considerations are pervasive in design as the substance through which designers' intentions are embodied. Likewise, Gant (2005) emphasizes that the strategic use of materials is one of the most influential way through which designers engender deeper more emotive connections between their products and their users. In literature, many conjoin on the significant role of materials in creating products' values (Arabe, 2004; Conran 2005; Cupchik, 1999; Ferrante et al, 2000; Gant, 2005; Karana, 2004; Lefteri, 2001, 2005; Ljungberg and Edwards, 2003; Macdonald, 2001; Mcdonagh et al, 2002; Rognoli and Levi, 2004; Zuo et al., 2005). Subsequently, interaction with materials, such as in products, can arise from not only the objective qualities of materials (like the physical ones) but also from the subjective experiences, which can vary from context to context for people (Crilly et al., 2004).

We see that materials can partly designate products' values and product experiences. The question however is, to what extend do people take materials into consideration in their products evaluations? And, which material experiences parameters do they use for evaluating materials? We are therefore interested in how people describe the materials of products. To find out the answers for these two main questions, we defined the following sub-questions:

- Do people give descriptions directly related with materials while evaluating products?
- Which parameters are mostly used in product descriptions?
- Do their descriptions change based on a product category?
- How people describe materials of products?
- Which parameters are mostly used in material descriptions?

And finally:

- For which product categories are materials taken as an effective evaluation criterion?

This paper consists of a field study conducted with people who live alone or with their friends, and have the chance to create their own private environment with their own preferred products. The results led to two models representing the parameters used in product evaluations and material evaluations, the (1) Product and (2) Material Experiences Evaluation

Models. The definition of material experiences and its parameters are explained in the next section. In section 3 the methodology of the field study is explained, followed by the results in section 4. The models are presented and discussed in section 5.

2 Material Experiences

The experiences with products are defined as the entire set of effects that are elicited by the interaction between user and a product (Hekkert, 2006, in press). Experiences consist of several dimensions such as materials, use, and function. While interaction with a product, a person (observer) first comes across the artefact, senses it, perceptually analyses it, compares it with the previous cases, classifies it into a meaningful category, and consequently interprets and appraises it (Hekkert, 2006, in press).

Materials, providing an interface between people and products, can also be appraised with experiences parameters. For instance, while describing a material in a particular context, besides the physical characteristics, one can talk about its colour, transparency and softness (sensorial properties of materials). In addition, one can talk about the materials' utility for hygienic environments and its appropriateness for several kinds of applications (use of materials) or its modernity, sobriety, robustness, prettiness (perceptions of materials). Furthermore, a person can tell how a material conjures up grandparents, high-technology, or foods (associations of materials), or how he/she gets happy or bored by materials (emotions evoked by materials). These main parameters can be used as *material experiences* parameters. The brief definitions of these material experiences parameters adapted from the product experiences domain can be found in coming sections.

2.1 Physical descriptions of materials

All quantifiable characteristics of materials, like strength, weight, conductivity, as well as descriptions related to the manufacturing techniques are taken as *physical* parameters in this study.

2.2 Use descriptions of materials

These are the aspects related to use and ergonomics, such as; “This material makes this product user-friendly”, or “The material of this product is easy to use with wet hands”, which are some examples from our case study explaining the *use* parameters.

2.3 Sensorial descriptions of materials

The interaction between the material and the user through senses, that is, all descriptions related to the sensorial properties of materials are appraised as the *sensorial* parameters for this study; such as, tactile aspects like smooth, cold, flowing, or visual aspects like matt, translucent, shiny and red.

2.4 Perceptive descriptions of materials

Bonapace (2002) defines the perception as how much the individual takes in after the signal has passed through the person's psycho- sensorial filters and the meaning the person attributes it. Staying close to Bonapace's definition, the *perceptive* parameters can be defined with two things. Firstly, what we think about materials after the sensation and secondly, the meaning we attribute to materials, like aggressive, pretty, modern and secure.

2.5 Associative descriptions of materials

With respect to the attribution of meanings to materials, associations play a noteworthy role as well as perceptions. Associations are defined by Ashby and Johnson (2003) as the things a product reminds you of, the things a product suggests. The *associative* parameters require the retrieval from memory and past experiences, and finding the things a particular material brings to mind; such as the association of holey polyurethane foam with a piece of cheese, or a colourful, transparent, elastic plastic with childhoods' jellybeans.

2.6 Emotional descriptions of materials

We define the emotional descriptions of materials as focusing on the subjective feelings (Desmet, 2003) of people while describing a material; that is, how a material makes you feel. "It makes me feel comfortable" or "this material surprises me" are two example descriptions of *emotions* parameters.

3 Methodology

Three pilot studies were conducted before finalizing the study. In the pilot studies the formulation of the questions, the order of the questions and the length of the study was assessed. After the first and second pilot study, we made slight changes. Based on the results obtained from the third pilot study no changes were made, therefore we decided to include it in the final study.

3.1 Participants

A total of 16 participants (11 male, 5 female) attended this study. Seven participants were students at a technical university (three in architecture, two in industrial design engineering, one in aerospace engineering, one in civil engineering) and one was a student at a medical university. Eight participants were employed as programmer, advisor, policeman, researcher (four) and entrepreneur/ DJ. All participants spoke English reasonable (four) to fluently (twelve). Participants' ages ranged from 21 to 31 with a mean of 25,5 years.

3.2 Product categories

The categories used in the study were: (1) a small electronic product, (2) a product made of a material liked by the participants, (3) a product made of a material disliked, (4) a product with a well distinct function like sitting/ storing/ eating or writing on it/ lighting, (5) a big electronic product, (6) a favourite product.

The first product category, *small electronic*, contained products that can be carried easily by people. The aim of the evaluation of this product category was to assess the participants' approach to the materials of the electronic objects which they touch frequently everyday. We also included the big electronic objects in this study as another product category, which cannot be carried easily by users, since we expected to find a differentiation between their preferences about the materials of these two groups of electronics. However, we did not put these two product categories after each other so that the participants were less able to compare them. For this reason, *big electronic* was the fifth product category of this study.

The second and the third products came directly from the topic of this study; that is materials. We asked them to select two products in the categories *liked materials* and *disliked materials*. The aim was to assess which of the material evaluation parameters dominate their selections.

The fourth product category was based on the functionality of the products; *function of* Four functions were selected for this category namely an object used for sitting, storing, eating or writing on (like a table or a coffee table) and for lighting. Although we did not use any definite word related to 'function' for this group of products, we aimed to collect data about the participants' preferences about the materials of an object preferred clearly relying on its function, as well as its other values like sensorial or perceptive.

The last product category was the participants' *favourite* product. Because people may tend to be more descriptive about the things they like, we found this category valuable as one of our product categories.

3.3 Procedure

The participants were informed with a letter about the product categories, from which they were asked to select a product beforehand. The study took place at the participant's home. They were not paid for participating and a session took approximately one hour per participant.

The sessions were divided into two phases: a product phase and a material phase. In the product phase participants were asked to describe the products they selected one by one, in the same order of categories for every participant. The first assignment was to describe the product in the participant's own words, followed by a summarizing question of describing the product in keywords. For every product, we additionally asked to compare the selected product to a product with similar functionality or similar materials (for the *liked materials* and *disliked materials* categories only). The material phase started just after the participants had described their selected six products. Herein participants were asked to describe the materials of the products by answering questions similar to the questions in the product phase (in own words, in keywords, comparing). Because there appeared to be no distinguishable additions in the descriptions in comparing parts, we focussed on the own words and keywords parts. All answers were laid down on answer sheets by the researchers. Dutch answers were translated.

3.4 Analysis

From the participants' descriptions, the terms and fragments were derived and categorized into the seven description parameters used in this study (use, function, materials, sensorial properties, perceptions, associations and emotions). The terms were put into two datasheets (one for product descriptions and one for materials descriptions). For every parameter, the number of terms was then counted. For example participant x used the three *sensorial* parameters blue, transparent and soft to describe his favourite product. Both researchers categorized half of the sessions and together all data entries were discussed for getting a uniform categorization and minimizing the number of wrong categorized terms.

4 Results

The 16 participants selected a total of 96 products from the defined categories (**Table 1**). The number of terms used to describe the products and the materials of the products, and their distributions among the seven parameters can be found in the charts in **Table 2**.

Table 1. Selected products for different categories.

SELECTED PRODUCTS					
Small electronic	Liked materials	Disliked materials	Function of ...	Big electronic	Favourite
phone watch game boy digital camera mobile phone remote control mp3 player mobile phone mobile phone iPod iPod shuffle palm pc mobile phone iPod mobile phone iPod	iPod mini closet bed electric toothbrush jacket watch cap coat hard disk coat reflector bore machine mp3 player hand bag clock coffee can	mps cd player raincoat chair remote control kitchen-knife dryer sunglasses quilt tea cloth gethoblaster garlic press coffee machine plate bureau chair refrigerator table	Billy closet pillow closet desk dirty laundry basket pen poker suitcase chairs lamp storage box breadbox as closets sofa Ikea sofa Ikea book-shelf closet lamp	washing machine television coffee machine TFT screen laptop refrigerator printer television television computer DVD player microwave stereo computer television television	power ball guitar sunglasses calculator coffee table computer super Nintendo computer computer photo camera wallet laptop laptop digital camera DVD player Senseo

The overview of parameters used in the descriptions of all products is explained in section 4.1. In section 4.2, the differences between descriptions of products and descriptions of materials are evaluated based on the distribution of terms categorized in various parameters. In the last section, ‘selecting descriptive parameters for the model’, we explain how we selected the most used parameters per product category for profiling our models.

4.1 Overview of all products

Looking at the number of terms derived from all product descriptions in **Table 2**, we found that, the participants were more descriptive about products (694 terms) than materials (510 terms). This holds for all product categories, including the ‘liked materials’ and ‘disliked materials’ categories in which participants selected products based on the materials of these products. For each category, the total number of descriptive terms were approximately the same (about 120), except for the big electronic category (101 terms). The number of terms found in the materials descriptions ranged from 77 terms to 98 terms.

Considering the products' descriptions, *perception* and *function* parameters were used most frequently (164 terms and 150 terms respectively), followed by the *use* and *sensorial* parameters. In describing the materials of the products, *material labels*, such as plastics, glass or metals, were frequently used in most cases (235 terms). The second largest parameter was the *sensorial* descriptions of materials and they were used approximately half the number of times (115) than the material labels.

Overall, the main differences between product and material descriptions can be found in the *use*, *function* and *emotion* parameters. These parameters scored low in the material descriptions compared to the product descriptions. Relatively, the number of terms found in both conditions, participants used more terms categorized as *sensorial* and *associative* descriptions of materials than in the descriptions of products. While describing products, participants used more various parameters than while they were describing the materials. In the last condition, participants hardly used any terms related to the *use* and *emotions* parameters.

4.2 Overview of product categories

In table 2, the parameters mostly used were coloured. *Material labels* were found most frequently in the descriptions of materials for all product categories. Material labels are not a parameter of material experiences. Therefore, *material labels* were not used for further comparison of the materials descriptions in the different categories.

For the *small electronic* category, the *sensorial* parameters (24) were mostly used to describe the materials of the products and were mentioned at least four times more than the rest of the parameters. While describing the products from this category, *sensorial* parameters were also frequently used (22), but not as frequent as *perceptive* (34) and *function* parameters (29).

The number of terms under *sensorial* parameter for the *big electronic* category was only half of the number (12) obtained from the *small electronic* category. Overall, the participants used fewer terms to describe the materials of the big electronics (except for materials labels) than for the small electronics. For both electronic categories, terms used to describe products' components, such as LED's or screens, were categorised as *others*.

Table 2: Number of parameters used in describing 16 products per category and its materials

	Terms used in describing products	Terms used in describing materials
ALL PRODUCTS	<p>ALL PRODUCTS</p> <p>Sum of terms for products: 694 for materials: 510</p>	<p>ALL PRODUCTS</p>
	<p>Small electronic</p> <p>Sum of terms for products: 118 for materials: 82</p>	<p>Small electronic</p>
	<p>Liked materials</p> <p>Sum of terms for products: 120 for materials: 87</p>	<p>Liked materials</p>
	<p>Disliked materials</p> <p>Sum of terms for products: 117 for materials: 77</p>	<p>Disliked materials</p>

Table 2 (continued) Number of parameters used in describing 16 products per category and its materials

There is a large difference between the terms used for describing products and the materials of the products in the *liked materials* category. Most terms for material descriptions were categorized under *sensorial* parameters (30) followed by *perception* (11). This was the other way around for the product descriptions: most terms were found in *perception* (33) and a fewer number in *sensorial* (15). Other material experiences parameters were hardly used in

material descriptions, although in the product descriptions *emotions* (10), *function* (22) and *use* (20) parameters were frequently found.

In the *disliked materials* category, most terms from the material descriptions were categorised as *perception* (11) or *sensorial* parameters (12). However, not many terms were found. The distribution of the terms used in the product descriptions of the *liked materials* and the *disliked materials* categories were similar.

Products in the category of *function of ...* were mostly described in *perceptive* terms (29). *Function* parameters (20) were frequently used in this category and the number of terms was comparable with the numbers of the terms under *sensorial* (23) and *use* (19) parameters. In this category, though not many terms were found, most terms from the materials description were also classified under the *perception* (12) or *sensorial* (13) parameters.

Remarkably, most of the terms coming from the *favourite* category were under the *function* parameter (29). The *use* (23), *perception* (24) and *emotions* (17) parameters were also frequently found in these product descriptions. Most terms from the materials descriptions were found in the *favourite* category (98). These terms were categorized mostly as *sensorial* (23) and *perception* (15) parameters.

4.3 Selecting descriptive parameters for the model

For the purpose of creating a material experiences evaluation model (MEEM) we made a distinction between the frequency in which parameters were found. A parameter was counted as frequently found when the number of terms found in 16 sessions exceeded 16. This number indicates that on average every participant mentioned this parameter at least once. We found this acceptable for including this parameter in the profile. The included parameters were pointed out with the ‘dotted border lines’ in table 2.

In every product category the *perception* and *function* parameters were used more than 16 times in the product descriptions. The *association* parameter and *others* were never found more than 16 times. The rest of the parameters differ per product category whether they were included in the product experiences parameter profile.

In the *small electronic* category the *sensorial* product experiences parameters were included, in the *liked materials* category the *use* and *materials* parameters and in the *disliked materials* category the *sensorial* and *materials* parameters were included. In the *function of ...* category the *sensorial* and *use* parameters were included and in the *big electronic* category the *use* and *sensorial* parameters. Lastly, in the *favourite* category the *use* and *emotion* parameters were included. Looking at the parameter profiles for the product descriptions we found a distinction between the different categories.

In the material descriptions, only *sensorial* parameters were used more frequently than 16 times, but only in three product categories. These were the *small electronics*, *liked materials* and *favourite* categories, which were included in the material experiences profile.

5 Product and Material Experiences Evaluation Models and Discussion

Based on the results from the experiments, two models were created for explaining people's evaluation of products in product experience parameters (the Product Experiences Evaluation Model- PEEM) and material experiences parameters (the Material Experiences Evaluation Model- MEEM). The first model summarizes the distribution of the frequently used product experiences parameters for each product category (Figure 1). The parameters for each category were selected based on the 'border box' explained in the previous section. The same approach was used for the creation of the second model, which elucidates what kinds of material experiences parameters were often used for describing the materials of the products from each category (Figure 2).

Figure 1 Product Experiences Evaluation Model (PEEM)

Figure 2 Material Experiences Evaluation Model (MEEM)

In the following, remarks concerning the questions of our study are summarized:

- According to the PEEM model people give descriptions directly related to materials while evaluating products. Most descriptions about the materials in the PEEM model were seen at the *disliked materials* and *liked materials* categories. However, the materials descriptions about the *disliked materials* and the *liked materials* category in the MEEM model were quite nominal. We explain this result by the eagerness of the participants to explain their selection in the first part of the questionnaire, in which they describe the products. When we particularly asked about the materials of these

products in the second part of the interviews, they had already given answers to this question, and might not have wanted to repeat their explanations.

- For product descriptions, the *functional* and *perceptive* parameters were both leading in all product categories. Other parameters changed based on the product categories.
- In some categories the function of the product is more clear than in others. Therefore, people tended to be more expressive about the other parameters of these products rather than function. For example, *sensorial* descriptions were only included in *small electronic*, *big electronic*, *function of...*, and the *disliked materials* categories.
- The emotional descriptions of products can merely be taken as a considerable parameter for the *favourite* category. This can be explained with the participants' emotional attachment to their favourite product. However, it is strange that even some of the favourite products were from other categories, like big electronics (such as lap tops), or small electronics (such as I-pod mini), we hardly found emotional descriptions in these particular categories.
- Overall the participants were most extensive in describing their favourite products. Another interesting point about the *favourite* category is that, participants were very descriptive about the function of these products. Generally we can say that, people are willing to talk about their favourite products.
- People described the materials mostly with the *sensorial* properties of materials, especially for the *favourite*, *liked materials* and *small electronic* categories. Other parameters were not considerable used. The common point among these three categories is that the interaction with these products is more tactual; that is, they are used frequently and they are easy to hold and use. If we look at this result from another perspective, we can say that the sensorial properties of materials play a crucial role in people's materials evaluations and can be effective in their preferences, as like in their favourite products categories.
- Participants used more terms to describe the materials of the *big electronic* products compared to *small electronic* products, mainly describing materials labels. The large number of materials labels can be explained by the fact that these products are bigger and contain more materials, but also have bigger surfaces showing the materials. Excluding the materials labels, the participants were less talkative about other material experiences parameters in the *big electronic* category. Daily interaction with *big electronic* products does not usually provide tactual interaction, holding or grasping.

Therefore, the low tactual contact with these products might have made the participants less descriptive about sensorial aspects of the materials.

The following remarks can be made regarding the product categories for which materials are an effective evaluation criterion:

The participants did not give a considerable amount of descriptions directly related to materials in their product descriptions. In our categorisation of terms we included most of the sensorial properties such as colour and texture in the *sensorial* product experiences parameter although they can also be considered as aspects of materials. For the assessment of the product descriptions part, we only counted the descriptions as ‘material descriptions’, if the participants mentioned the materials of these products specifically. The way we categorized the terms can therefore explain why not many descriptions directly related to materials were found in the product descriptions part.

This study was performed with a limited number of participants. Therefore, instead of giving sharp arguments about the material experiences evaluations, we prefer drawing a wide-ranging overview about these contacts. For further studies and for more reliable results, we strongly recommend working with a greater number of participants. Moreover, some of the descriptions had ambiguous meanings, which made them difficult to classify; such as, *cold*, *warm* and *firm*, which can be evaluated as both sensorial and perceptive descriptions. We assessed them individually in their particular contexts.

Although people try to explain the materials of the products as individual substances, it is difficult to evaluate them without any context. For instance, even though the emotional descriptions of materials were defined as an individual parameter in material experiences, it is hardly effective in people’s material descriptions. Because, most of the time people form emotional bonds with the products rather than the materials. Thus, an attachment or an emotional bond cannot be easily afforded by only the materials of products. In other words, material experiences are formed based on the material usage contexts, or products they embody.

6 Conclusions

Throughout this study, we tried to find out the answers for two main questions: to what extent do people take materials into consideration in their products evaluations? And, which material experiences parameters do they use for evaluating materials? The results of this study show that people only evaluate materials when they are specifically asked to describe a product that was selected for its materials. While evaluating the materials of products, people do not merely concentrate on the physical characteristics of materials but also some non-physical ones, such as sensorial characteristics or perceptive characteristics of materials. For this reason, as like the product experiences, we can talk about the material experiences, which explains how people interact with the materials of products and what kinds of characteristics of materials compose this interaction. According to this study, the sensorial characteristics of materials are the most distinctive parameters in material experiences.

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